

Impact of Globalization on Urban Slum Dwellers- Migrants from Rural Areas: A Social Case Study of Barasat Town, North 24- Parganas District, West Bengal

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Abstract

The following demonstrates the relationship between globalization process and its impact on urban slumdwellers of West Bengal, A case study was conducted on Barasat Town of North 24 Pargana of West Bengal. The study suggests the creatorship between global economic change and growth of slum areas. It deals with the narration of the lifestyle of the slum dwellers of present days. The study has also interrogated the impact of various developmental program like JNNURM by the government and their implications.

Keywords: Globalization, Slum, Urban, Migration, Urban Social Problems , JNNURM

Introduction

The alarming increase in the number of migrating workers from rural areas during the few decades has resulted in a rapid increase of population in the urban areas all over India. With the advent of globalization, liberalization and privatization during early nineties, there has been an increase in the job opportunities especially in the service sectors and informal sector. Moreover, the subsidies being withdrawn from the agriculture sector as per International Monetary Fund-World Bank imposition, has resulted in making traditional agriculture a non-profitable option.

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The acquisition of land for various developmental programmes has also resulted in landless, jobless peasants. Thus, many marginal and poor peasants have been forced to migrate to urban areas for their livelihood and work as semi-skilled and unskilled worker. They work at various service sectors and informal sectors and live in slums. Many spend their nights on pavements. With this crowding, there is an encroachment in various areas and an ever-increasing demand for water, electricity, health, education and other essential commodities. This has resulted in many social evils like rise in anti-social activities, social unrest etc. This overcrowding has also disturbed the local natural environment. The slums having no proper sanitation have polluted the entire area resulting in many instances of health hazards. The local Govt. like municipalities and corporations are unable to provide civic amenities at this juncture to these migrants. This paper mainly tries to examine the social study of such migrating urban slum dwellers and in analyzing their struggles against an undesirable environment and formulating strategies to improve their living standard. The methodology of the research work would be used mainly from primary and secondary sources.

Concept of Globalization

Some people feel that the concept of globalization is the free movement of trade, investment, services and exchange of culture world over. But according to some experts, globalization is integration of nation's economic system with the international market forces. Ironically, some others describe globalization as a strategy of the imperialist forces to loot the 'Third World' countries. In fact, globalization is the mobility of finance capital across the world, particularly of the poor countries. The unprecedented technological progress has enabled the easy flow of finance capital at the fastest speed to any country.

In the process of globalization, the three International Institutions namely, International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank (WB) and World Trade Organization (WTO) play a major role. These three organizations in a close collaboration function as the "Intelligence Agencies" on the economic policies of the underdeveloped countries. And lastly, some feel that Globalization stands for the ultimate rights of multinational companies to allocate resources according to their own criteria.

Globalization in India

Globalization, liberalization and privatization started in India during 1991 when Govt. of India implemented New Economic Policy under the directives of IMF-WB along with their desired impositions. One such imposition was that the Govt. of India should gradually withdraw the subsidies from the agricultural sector. As a result, the cost of production in cultivation has increased manifold, making traditional farming an unprofitable option for the Indian farmers. On the other hand, land acquisitions in the name of various developmental projects have rendered many peasants landless and jobless. According to NSSO (56th round) Report, 40 percent of the farmers have expressed their desire to quit farming. Thus, many marginal and poor peasants have been forced to migrate to urban areas for their livelihood. According to the *National Crime Bureau* record, in the ten years period between 1998 and 2008 as many as 2 lakh farmers committed suicide in India. Globalization has created several push and pull factors for common people in India. The push factors are mainly the result of the requirement of land for big developmental projects, industries and SEZ etc. whereas the pull factors are mainly to availability of jobs and lucrative economic opportunities in urban areas.

Urbanization in India

Urbanization is an indicator of economic development. Employment opportunities attract people to settle in urban areas. The Eleventh Five Year Plan of the Government of India notes that '....the contribution of the urban sector to India's GDP has increased from 29 percent in 1950-51 to 47 percent in 1980-81. The urban sector presently contributes about 62 - 63 percent of the GDP and this is expected to increase to 75 percent by 2021'. The trend of urbanization in India in recent decades is attributed to the economic reforms initiated in the year 1991. India's total population increased about 2.8 times between 1951 and 2001, but the urban population rose about 4.6 times during the same period. As per the Census of 2001, India's urban population was 286.1 million comprising 27.8 per cent of the total population of 1028.6 million. The Census of India classified as many as 5161 towns in 2001, which was 472 more than 1991 Census (4689). Out of the total 5161 towns, 3800 are statutory towns which mean the towns having

municipality, corporation or cantonment board etc. and 1361 are census towns which means a town having a minimum population of 5000 with a population density of 400 people per sq. km., at least 75 percent of male which are working population engaged in non-agricultural pursuits.

This rapid increase in urban population has led to a tremendous pressure on civic amenity system like water supply, drainage, solid waste management, transport etc. In many cities, the problems of the traffic congestion, pollution, poverty, social unrest are assuming alarming proportions.

Migration in India

As a consequence to the neo-liberal policies followed by the successive Governments, although there has been serious income disparities and agrarian distress, there has been a vast growth of informal economy which has resulted in rapid migration from rural to urban areas. The total migrants as per the census of 1981 were 213 millions, in 1991 census it was 232 million and 2001 census it is 315 millions. As per the census of the year 1991, nearly 20 million people migrated to urban areas seeking their livelihood. Within a decade, the number of inter-state migration almost doubled to 41 million. These migrating people work as semi skilled and unskilled worker. Mostly, they work as contractual labour at various service sectors and informal sectors and live in slums. It is to be noted that both the 2001 Census and the National Sample Survey of 2002 estimated that every seventh person in urban India was a slum dweller. According to 2001 census, 42.6 million populations live in slums. This constitutes 15 percent of the total urban population of the country.

Keeping in view the above features a social case study was done in *Barasat Town* on slum dwellers who migrated from rural areas for their livelihood. The objectives of the study are :

1. Causes of migration and affects of globalization on them.
2. The type of works they are engaged in & condition of living and source of livelihood.
3. To suggest a few strategies for their development

West Bengal

Barasat Town : An Overview

Barasat town is located at a distance of about 25 km from Kolkata. The latitude and longitude of Barasat town area is 88.482962 and 22.707002. Barasat is a municipal town established in the year 1869 and now is the district headquarters of North 24-Parganas in West Bengal. Its' area is 34.05 sq. km. and has a total population of 2.32 lakh as per census 2001. Males constitute 52 percent of the total population and females 48 percent. The literacy rate is 85.6 percent, it has 159 slums and out of the total

population of 55,168, 23.77 percent are living in the slums. The total area of slums is 4.78 sq. km. and the number of families living in slums is 12,957. All the wards in Barasat have slum dwellers. The town is mainly a commercial place with many Govt. establishments and a session judge court with many schools, colleges and a State University. Rapid urbanization of Barasat is due to the demographic explosion and poverty induced rural- urban migration. The migration is directly or indirectly linked with the affects of globalization. The town which originally had 18 municipal wards in 1991 has now been divided into 32 municipal wards owing to the rapid increase in population. A general information of Barasat

Municipality has been shown in table no. I.

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Established in	1869	No. of Wards	32
Population	231521 (Census-2001)	Population of Male	1.18 lakh
Population of Female	1.13 lakh	Minority Population	25875
SC Population	32855	ST Population	1555
No. of Holdings	81880	Electricity coverage	85 percent
Total of Slum	159	Total Population of slum	55168
Total area of Slum	4.78 sq. km.	No. of family of slum	12957

Source : Barasat Municipality

Causes of Migration

Since 1991 when globalization started in India, its adverse impacts affected rural Bengal as it did the other States. According to the data of Govt. of West Bengal in 1990s the food grains production was 5.84 per cent but in 1996-97 this was decreased to a mere average of 2.39 per cent. During this period, the cost of production had increased due to an increase in the prices of harvesting materials. The increase in prices of irrigation was 147.7 percent and fertilizer was 78.36 percent. The prices of various other harvesting items too increased, resulting in the decline of the production of the food grains. The increase in the cost of production in the agricultural sector forced

many farmers to give up their occupation of agriculture as they could not cope up with ever increasing prices. They were left with no other alternatives but to look for some other means of livelihood for their survival. In West Bengal too, though land reforms had been implemented, a large number of poor and marginal peasants have been forced to opt for other means of livelihood instead of agriculture. All these people thus move to urban areas looking for odd jobs for surviving. Most of them are unskilled or semi skilled and whatever jobs they get in urban areas force them to live in slums.

The slum dwellers of Barasat town are mostly migrants from its surrounding rural areas because of the above mentioned reasons. Most of them were poor, marginal peasants and landless agricultural workers when they lived in the villages. The harvesting expenses increased year after year. Most of them fell into debt trap. Some of the poor and marginal peasants committed suicides due to huge debt. The field survey report of *Berachampa village* in North 24-Parganas as given in Table-II clearly demonstrates how the increase in production cost affects the income of a peasant.

Table-II Harvesting Expenses of Aman* Paddy per bigha (Base Year=2008)

Sl. No.	Harvesting Expenses		Amount (Rs.)
1	Tractor Expenses	@ Rs.150/- per hour x 2=30 hrs.	375=00
2	Agricultural Labour expenses :		
	(a) Resizing field	@ Rs.60/- x 1=	60=00
	(b) Paddy Plant (roya)	@ Rs.60/- x 6=	360=00
	(c) Weeding	@ Rs.60/- x 2=	120=00
3	Seeds cost	@ Rs.200 per bigha	200=00
4	Paddy Cutting, Bundles etc.	@ Rs.60/- x 3=	180=00
5	Carrying charges from field	@ Rs.60/- x 3=	180=00
6	Jharai	@ Rs.60/- x 3=	180=00
7	Fertilizers Charges	@ Rs.10/- x 20 bags	200=00
8	Pesticides Spray	@ Rs. 150/- per lit.	150=00
Total Expenses :			2005=00

Source: Field Survey in Berachampa village of North 24-Pgs.

Approx. 10 jute bags rice are obtained from 1 bigha of land (1 bag contains of 60 kg. of rice). These bags have been sold in the open market of this village at an average rate of Rs.600/- per bag. Thus the total

earning of a peasant amounted to Rs.600/- x 10= Rs.6000/-. And their expenses amounted to Rs.2005/- or say Rs.2000/-. The net income of a peasant is (Rs.6000-2000)=Rs.4000/- per bigha (1 acre=3.25 bigha). If a poor peasant has 3 bighas of cultivation land, he can earn hardly Rs.4000/- x 3= Rs.12000/- in a year through Aman cultivation and including the other earning from cultivation of *aus*, vegetables, etc., one can earn around Rs.4000/- per annum. The total income is Rs.12,000+Rs.4,000/-=Total Rs.16,000/-. The monthly average income of a marginal peasant owning 3 bighas of land is estimated at Rs.1,334/- only. If a marginal peasant has 1(one) bigha of land then his average monthly income is Rs.445/-. All these negative syndrome forces poverty induced migration of rural poor peasants to urban informal sectors.

(*Three crops of paddy are grown in West Bengal *aman*, *aus* and *boro*. Aman is the main paddy crop. Aman and aus are both

kharif crops and boro is a crop harvested in the summer. Kharif crops are sown in the monsoon).

Table no.-III shows the increase of slums & slum dwellers between 1991 and 2011 in Barasat Town.

Table-III Increase of slums & slum dwellers in numbers in Barasat Town

Year	Slums	Slums dwellers
1991	45(28.31%)	10,147(18.39%)
2011	114(71.69%)	45,021(81.61%)
Total :	159(100%)	55,168(100%)

Source: Field Survey and Barasat Municipality

It is clear from the above table that the numbers of slums and slum dwellers have increased in Barasat town after the implementation of New Economic Policy in India during 1991. Slums increased from 28.31 percent to 71.69 percent and the increase in slum dwellers was from 18.39 percent to 81.61 percent between 1991 and 2011. The percentage of slum children (0-6 years), literacy rate and literacy rate of women in the slum of Barasat town is shown in the table-IV given below:

Table No. IV

Percentage of slum children (0-6) to slum	Literacy Rate (slum)	Female Literacy (slum)
11.77	76.53	70.39

Source : Provisional Population Totals, Series-20, HDR-North 24-Pgs., West Bengal

Occupational Structure & Living Condition

Globalization, liberalization and privatization through apparently seems to have aided the generation of employment scope in India, but in reality it has acted as a negative factor. Under globalization, survival and existence of the poor are affected adversely. Liberalization which permits cheap import of goods directly or indirectly affects the agriculture, handicraft and cottage industries. The rural economy is thus adversely affected and so the poor rural people have to face the consequences. The benefits of liberalization generally accrue to only those who acquire new skills. It is unlikely that common man and the poor will benefit from liberalization. Privatization causes retrenchment of workers. Most of these cities using capital intensive technologies can not generate employment for these distressed rural poor. So there is a transfer of rural poverty to urban poverty. Poverty induced migration of illiterate and unskilled labourer occurs in cities and towns in India.

Barasat town is no exception. It is also facing the same problem of migration as the other cities and towns in India. Most of the rural migrating poor people live in slums. Usually the slum dwellers are mostly involved in labour based work in the informal sectors. Very few are engaged in the organized sector as they do not possess any formal training to procure decent jobs.

Occupations of slum dwellers in Barasat town

Table - V

Various Occupation	In Percentage
House maid, night guards etc.	12
Daily Labourer	55
Petty Businessmen	5
Rickshaw puller & Driver	20
Vendors	8

Source : Field Survey

From the above table, it is found that the majority of the workers among slum people are engaged as daily labourers (55 percent), followed by rickshaw pullers and drivers (20 percent). Among the slum community, 12 percent are engaged in different types of services. Most slum women are engaged as house maid, males are engaged as nights guards, security guards etc. 8 percent are engaged in vendors profession like vegetable sellers, train hawkers etc. This shows that the trend of employment from different sources is mainly based on hard physical working capabilities. Here in particular, most of the rickshaw pullers stay in jhuggies, owner's workshops or below staircases, on footpaths, under hanging balconies on the roadside, in the rickshaws or even in open space. The stressful life with no rest day coupled with unhygienic living conditions and limited food results in poor health of most workers. Diseases like tuberculosis, asthma, hernia, weak eyesight and underweight are common. They have no medical insurance or access to health care facilities. Many families whose kids used to go to school earlier have been forced to drop out simply because they have no affordable income. Most of the Barasat slum houses are very small and are usually made of mud and bamboos. Some are also made of *Tin* in different wards. The environment of the slums is very congesting and unhygienic. The inhabitants suffer from inadequate service of civic amenities. As they need to cook in order to feed themselves and their families, they have to cook in the same room where they live using coal, cow dung, kerosene or wood as fuel which further pollutes the environment resulting in various health hazards. Another vulnerable aspect of the slums is the women trafficking and smuggling of goods. The highly porous West Bengal-Bangladesh border is used for smuggling goods. In some of the areas the trafficking is done by utilizing women and even the minors are inducted in this profession. As per police record in 2009, 8 cases of anti-human trafficking were registered. The number of victims that were rescued was 6 and 5 traffickers were arrested in the police raids.

Making Kolkata a 'London city'

The new Govt. of West Bengal announced that they will make Kolkata the London of West Bengal. Thus, a series of plans to reconstruct the city have been formulated. Among which a number of high rise buildings would be set up, the development of Ganga riverfront as an

expanded space of leisure, the installation of a number of entry gates in the different corners of the city are being planned. But implementations of all these plans are associated with the eviction of urban poor living in slums. For example, the recent eviction of Nonadanga slum dwellers. The earlier West Bengal Govt. also enthusiastically introduced similar urban development programmes which were also associated with the displacement and eviction of the poor people following the prescription of the *Jawaharlal Nehru National Urban Mission* (JNNURM). Although Barasat Municipality does not have adequate funds, it is installing decorative lamps for beautification and spending a lot of money under JNNURM project for implementing such plans.

A careful analysis shows that the timing of the implementation of JNNURM coincided with a number of anti-people blueprints under the new economic policies involving eviction and displacement of poor people.

The brunt of urbanization has been felt by these poor migrants in Barasat town also. For the extension of Metro Rail, eviction notice has been served to those people living beside the railway tracks. No adequate compensations or alternate arrangement for their rehabilitation has been offered to them. The demographic explosion in Barasat town has resulted to innumerable flat construction. Many of which have been constructed on wetlands or agricultural lands which in turn has affected the local natural environment. The real estate business has indirectly resulted in helping many antisocial activities and created many antisocial who have become a threat to the locality. The large numbers of constructions of Malls, Restaurants, and Shopping Complexes etc., have been welcomed by the richer section but the poor people are unable to cope up with this culture. Thus the void between the richer section and poorer section has widened. This division has given rise to many socio-economic problems. The slum dwellers and rural migrants being the poorest are facing a great crisis where their very existence is at stake.

Conclusion

It can be concluded that New Economic policy which is associated with Globalization is mainly responsible for poverty, migration, peasants' distress etc. Under the impact of globalization the rich are becoming richer day by day and the poor are becoming poorer causing glaring socio-economic disparities in the Indian society. In India there are two types of Indian. 10 percent is the elite group of the total population, while 90 percent live an existence of utmost poverty. The report of *National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector* says, 77 percent of Indian population live on rupees 20/- or less per day. The withdrawal of food subsidies, drastic reduction in the benefits of the Public Distribution System, rise in prices of essential commodities, taxes on common people, concessions given to big business houses, etc. are few examples of the attack of globalization on common people in India. So it should be the prime task of common people to intensify the struggles against globalization and pressurize Govts. to withdraw the conditions imposed by IMF-WB.

Both Central and State Governments have launched several programmes such as Urban Basic Services for the Poor (UBSP), Comprehensive Slum Improvement Programmes (SCIP), National Slum Development Programme (NSDP) and Basic Minimum Services (BMS) with a view to alleviate urban poverty including environmental improvement of the slums and socio-economic development of the poor in recent years. But it is not sufficient. Govt. should take initiative at local level with intensive methods to sort out the problems and take various measures for the implementation of plans and programmes to solve it. The employment opportunities should be generated for the slum people. The civic amenities should be improved so that it can be provided to all the urban people including the slums dwellers. Integration of rural and urban economy can be achieved by emphasizing on agro-based industries where the raw material would be processed in rural economy and then transferred to urban economy through industries. Urban planning and housing with human face should be implemented for slum people. *Land Reform Programmes* should be continued by the Govt. taking all the necessary steps for helping the peasants in order to minimize the rural migration. A careful and proper planning is needed for urban development.

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